

DISTANCE EDUCATION: HOW TO TEACH LESSONS AT ZOOM

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Due to the closure of schools, lyceums and universities for quarantine, the demand for working in an online format has risen sharply. So, you have a need to conduct distance learning: how to do it and master it quickly! In this article, let's look at how to competently organize distance learning in Zoom, if you have not tried this format before.

In order for the online lesson to go well, you need to choose the optimal type of communication with the student/students, choose online tools for presenting the training material and organize these materials (it is better to do everything immediately online and stored on virtual disks, so that you and the student have access from any device).

Contemporary realities are forcing us to look for new ways of learning with the latest information technology. In the shortest time we, foreign language teachers, had to choose from the huge number of educational platforms and services offered those that would optimally help to continue the learning process, but already in the Internet space. A particularly effective, based on my personal experience, innovative form of work with students is the work on the educational platform ZOOM. It is worth noting that my choice in favor of ZOOM was not made by chance. I was guided by the online teaching experience of my colleagues, including those from abroad. What are the benefits of this service? In this report I will only look at the functionality of the system that I use the most in my work.

Today, the Zoom platform allows you to teach a class online just like a regular school class. To do this, you need to use some of the options and settings in the program. So, how do you replace the usual forms of work?

1: Teacher talks to the whole class.

You have to use Zoom's "big screen view" mode. Some teachers use at once "show screen" mode, when in the center there is demo material (textbook, presentation), and on the right side you can see video of participants in small windows. In fact, this is the second mode, the first is a general view of the class for oral communication, conversation.

This is how the teacher would begin a typical lesson with the class. All the children look at the teacher, the teacher organizes the class, asks questions. So, take the time to turn on the "demonstration", establish communication with the class using the "common screen view" which provides a frontal mode of working with the class.

2. the student's response at the board

This can be replaced by the "speaker's close-up" mode. When working with the class at the front, look for the "screen view" option in the upper right corner of the screen. This is how you activate the speaker's "close-up" mode. It could be a student giving a report, a message, or telling a poem.

3. express questioning.

A quick answer to a teacher's question in front of the class can replace the student's answer from the screen by using the "space" key on the computer.

The Zoom platform is known to be technically very sensitive, so conference participants are asked to mute the sound. Not all teachers know that with this mode of operation, the student can quickly answer the teacher's questions without turning on their sound with the mouse. This involves pressing the space bar on the computer and holding it down. This allows students to quickly answer the teacher's questions when working with the class in front of them.

4. Raised Hand

Raising your hand in class is now available electronically. The option is called "Raise Your Hand." When a student clicks on the "raise your hand" icon, a blue palm sign appears on the screen. We need to get students used to raising their hands now electronically and it will gradually help the organization in a virtual space where it is especially difficult to handle a situation where everyone speaks at the same time.

5. Pointer

The teacher's pointer is being replaced by the "tracking" option. The commenting tools in the Zoom options include a "tracking" option, namely a red light, to highlight the desired material. The teacher can use the feature as a pointer, successfully drawing students' attention to the main thing while demonstrating and explaining the material.

6. Blackboard.

The action "make notes on the board in the classroom" can replace the possibility of making notes on the whiteboard in Zoom, which can be handled by more than one student.

7. Individual assignments

The performance of some exercises by all the students at the same time in their exercise-books can be replaced by writing in chat. To prevent students from seeing each other's answers, you need to set the chat properly - "allow only the organizer to send messages". Then students' answers are sent only to the teacher.

8. Working at the board

The usual mode of work in a real lesson, when all the students work in their notebooks and one student works at the blackboard, is preserved by the "T-text" commenting option. While students work in their workbooks and send their answers to the teacher in chat, one student can do a written exercise right on the screen in the

textbook. He uses the "T" text option. The other students can see him doing the exercise.

9. Favorite Red Paste.

Checking students' work with red paste. Whenever checking students' answers on the screen, a written exercise in the textbook, saved answers in the chat room, any written work, the teacher checks it all by using the "draw" comment option while selecting red. In essence, this is the usual checking of written work with red paste.

ZOOM is a cloud-based video conferencing platform that allows students to communicate online in an accessible, real-time format, which was a key factor for me in choosing the platform for teaching English online to high school students, because the functionality of ZOOM allows us as teachers to teach lessons as effectively as possible in a distance learning environment. The ZOOM platform offers communication software, which I think is one of the major advantages of the system, combining video conferencing, chat and collaboration between students and teachers via the various features provided by the ZOOM platform, for both sides of the educational process.

Foreign language learning involves face-to-face communication between students and teachers in a variety of ways and forms. The ZOOM platform fulfills these conditions, as the teacher - or organizer - creates the possibility to communicate both orally and in writing through the different features the system offers. For example, the teacher-organizer has a possibility to control a microphone, i.e. to organize audio and video perception for all participants, to create a kind of a language laboratory for practicing listening and reading skills, to demonstrate the screen of his digital device for displaying different information materials, including audio and video materials, presentations, electronic version of a textbook, visual materials.

The teacher can use the "annotate" function on the screen to highlight points that need to be emphasized or to perform various exercises, such as connecting words and pictures, or solving a crossword puzzle. Students can show the completed homework on their screen by implementing the "screen sharing" function, and the conference organizer, in turn, sees the student's screen on his/her own, corrects the assignment, and gives a grade. Another useful feature "chat" gives the opportunity to write questions and give answers to them without turning on the microphone, ie practicing writing skills, you can enter new lexical units for learning or send files and various kinds of documents immediately to all students or selectively, which helps to provide a differentiated approach to the teaching of foreign language in secondary schools. In addition, the platform includes an interactive whiteboard, which allows direct feedback to students in real time: the teacher has the ability to visually explain the material, give written assignments and directly in the lesson to check them, to practice the necessary lexical and grammatical material, to work with visual material.

One of the necessary functions for teaching a foreign language is the ability to record the lesson. The teacher is able to show the past lesson to those learners who for whatever reason could not be present in the online class at one time or another. In ZOOM we are able to divide students into pairs or groups to work on individual assignments such as the production of a dialogic or monologue statement, projects or a creative workshop. In this way teachers retain familiar working methods, effectively incorporating them into the new lesson format. In other words, ZOOM has many advantages, which make it indispensable for teachers of foreign languages during distance learning, but the most important advantage is that the platform allows the use of live speech in interaction with learners, without which learning a foreign language is a priori impossible, and thus contributes to the organization of full-fledged foreign language lessons in the complex environment of modern realities. Despite its clear and obvious advantages, the platform has some drawbacks, the most significant of which is the time limit of the session-40 minutes, which is enough for a traditional lesson in elementary and middle school, but not enough for high school students. Of course, like any online platform ZOOM presupposes high-speed Internet and a powerful digital device. Thus, the ZOOM platform seems to me, as a foreign language teacher, the most effective for conducting foreign language lessons in a distance learning environment because it allows us to preserve the most important and fundamental factor of the success of the acquisition of basic skills and abilities as communication, without which it is impossible to master language competence, which is the main result of foreign language teaching.

List of references:

1. Techniques and Principles in Language Teaching by Diane Larsen-Freeman and Marti Anderson.
2. A course in language teaching by Penny Ur.
3. Teaching English as a Second Or Foreign Language by Donna Brinton, Marguerite Ann Snow, and Marianne Celce-Murcia.

